

GENRE DIVERSITY IN CEREMONIAL CUSTOMS OF UZBEK-ENGLISH PEOPLE

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Annotation. In this article, special attention is paid to the diversity of genres in the wedding ceremony of the English and Uzbek peoples. In addition, the process of conducting English weddings will be discussed. Some notable aspects of Uzbek weddings are also discussed.

Key words: Handover of the bride, white dress, wedding ring, wedding cake, rice sprinkling, flower throwing.

The traditions and customs related to the wedding ceremony of the English and Uzbek peoples are similar in terms of content. And most importantly, at the heart of them are noble goals, such as laying a solid foundation for the family life of the bride and groom and preserving traditional customs in the newly formed family.

White dress. From time immemorial, British brides wore their best dresses on their wedding day. For many centuries, in English culture, color was not important for brides, and even black dress, which leaves a negative impression on most peoples, was worn at weddings. However, in the 19th century, when Queen Victoria appeared in a long white dress at the wedding of Prince Albert, this color made a special impression on the British. Since then, it has become customary to wear a white dress on the wedding night. This custom still adorns brides as a symbol of luxury and majesty.

Transferring the bride. On the wedding day, the bride's father takes her hands and hands them to the groom. It means: "The girl was the property of the father and now she is sold to the bridegroom."

Wedding ring. In English culture, on the wedding day, the bride and groom put wedding rings on each other's fingers and make wedding vows. A wedding ring is worn as a symbol of eternal love. The bride and groom hold each other's right hands and say the following marriage vows:

I, (name), take you, (name)
To be my wife/husband,
To have and to hold
From this day forward;
For better, foe worse,
For richer, for poorer,
In sickness and in health,
To love and to cherish,
Till death us do part,
According to God`s holy law.
In the presence of God I make this vow.

Meaning: As I (name) take you (name) as my wife/husband, I swear before God according to God's holy law to love and care for you from today, for better, for worse, in wealth, in poverty, in health, in sickness, until death do us part.

Sprinkle rice. On the wedding day, grains of rice or wheat are sprinkled on the heads of the bride and groom and the following wish is made: "May your life be abundant and wealthy". Meaning: "May your life be abundant and prosperous."

Wedding cake. For centuries, cake has been a traditional and beloved favor at British weddings. The leader: "So I'd like (bride) and ... (groom) to walk around to the front of the bridal table to perform their first duty as husband and wife" - calls the bride and groom. Meaning in Uzbek language: "So I ask ... (bride) and ... (groom) to come to the wedding table to fulfill their first duties as husband and wife." In front of the cake, the bride and groom hold one knife together with one hand and try to hold each other's hands with the other, that is, there is a view that whoever has the uppermost hand when cutting the cake will have priority in the family.

Throwing flowers. In the 11th century in Britain, an unusual custom was held at the end of a wedding. The guests who attended the wedding tried to snatch the bride's dress, flowers and even her hair. It was believed that the happiness and luck of the bride will be transferred to them through this. Later this tradition became cultural. In this case, the bride turns her back to the guests and throws the bouquet in her hand towards them, and it is believed that the guest who quickly hangs this flower (they are usually unmarried girls) will be lucky.

Carrying the bride from the threshold. This trick has been used since ancient times to reduce the excitement of the bride on the first night. It is also seen as a respect for her chastity. Uzbek people also wear special clothes on wedding days. These clothes differed depending on the region. For example, if Samarkand and Bukhara were of one type, those of Surkhan and Kashkadarya oasis were of the second type, Fergana was a separate type, Khorezm bride and groom had completely different clothes.

Contributes. This ceremony is held as a symbol of the bride-groom's bond for life, being shoulder to shoulder with each other, not leaving each other in good or bad, difficult or easy days, in health or illness. An elderly woman holding the bride's hand in one hand and the groom's hand in the other, joining the two, that is, holding hands. Then he prays as follows: "Be together until the end of your lives." "May your holding hands, your united paths never part"; "Be loyal to one another." Traditionally, the bride tries to take her hands away from the groom as a symbol of Ibo-hayo, but the groom does not let go of her hand. And those around support the groom: "Groom, be strong!" "Groom, show your strength!"

Footsteps. This ceremony is performed when the groom leaves the bride's house. In this, the groom steps on the bride's feet in the presence of relatives, groomsmen and friends of the bride. The meaning of this is that the person who steps first becomes the leader in the family. But in many cases, the bride puts her foot on the groom of her own free will. It is characterized by the influence of her religion and her upbringing in the family, where the man stands one step above her and recognizes the leadership of the man in the family.

Giving rice. When the bridegroom takes the bride away from her home, the bride's relatives mix rice and beans in a bowl and give it to them. This custom is done with the intention that two young people will have many children and live a prosperous life. "Be

happy"; "Increase yourselves like rice and beans, have sons and daughters"; It is blessed with expressions such as "Be a sovereign state and a sovereign child".

Yes, because the British are very sensitive to their traditions. And if some of them are similar to our wedding traditions, others are very different. At one time, England, like many other countries, did not like the desire of newlyweds to marry for love. And the marriage was prearranged. A three-year-old boy and girl could be considered "husband and wife" in advance. Then the age of marriage was increased to seven years. Some couples even ran away to get married in secret. Of course, there were times when such movements were suppressed even at the state level. Since England was divided into counties, it was possible to get married only in one of the counties where one of the spouses lived. This rule was valid until 1990.

Today, wedding traditions in England dictate to brides, as a rule, stricter requirements than clothes in Russian and European fashion. In English weddings, dresses with a wide waist and off the shoulders are rare. An English bride usually wears something new, blue or some other color. The shirt must be new. In general, the wedding dress is very rarely kept in English families. According to the belief that it brings good luck. Some brides get their wedding dress from a married relative who has children. A blue wedding dress is especially traditional because it is believed that this color repels evil spirits. The shoes worn by old girls for weddings were old. But, of course, few people want to go to the holiday in old shoes, so shoes that have been worn at least once before the holiday are considered old.

The British also preferred white dresses without any color decoration, traditionally with a long veil on the bride's head. It is considered a special tradition to wear white gloves at a wedding. But this custom, of course, is not always observed. In some counties of England it is customary to give the bride a bracelet with two small horseshoes. It is believed that this will bring him happiness. The look of the English groom: English guys also prefer not to deviate from the classics and choose a dark coat and a standard suit for the groom. According to tradition, English grooms should wear old shoes on their wedding day. However, today's youth are increasingly rejecting this practice.

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